

Illuminated Charters and AI - Impact of Modernizing the Monasterium.net Platform

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Monasterium.net is not only the largest European collection of data on charters but also a collaborative platform. A showcase for this is the “Illuminated Charters” project (IIIUrK), initiated by Martin Roland, Georg Vogeler and Andreas Zajic. This collection comprises over 4,400 documents enriched with decorative and graphical elements on three levels:

- Level 1 contains the most complex decoration: drawn or painted, historiated and/ or the use of colours [miniatures, initials, borders, coats of arms].
- Level 2 covers pen-drawn decoration [in rare cases including figurative and zoomorphic elements without references to the textual content].
- Level 3 denotes charter specific graphical elements [e.g. rota, chrismon, signum or monogram].

The data has been collected in various research projects (“Illuminated Charters as ‘Gesamtkunstwerk’”, “IIIUrK.

From electronic card index to research platform?” (Roland 2018), “Power and Diplomacy. The illuminated charters in France 1160-ca. 1420”) a s a cooperation of art historians (Gabriele Bartz, Martin Roland), diplomatics scholars (Andreas Zajic, Markus Gneiß, Jonathan Dumont), and digital humanists (Martina Bürgermeister, Niklas Tscherne, Georg Vogeler). Identifying such documents is difficult as existing archival descriptions mostly don't include their visual appearance. Describing the decoration of documents is an additional challenge as deep art historical knowledge is necessary. Thus, the “Illuminated Charters”-collection includes a glossary aggregating information on overarching topics (Bartz, Roland 2014-2025). The poster will describe how the development of a new version of Monasterium.net can contribute to reduce the impact of these problems, while the problem of detection and annotation of decoration and images in textual sources is certainly generalisable.

Monasterium.net was built as a classical XML-based database based on eXist-db. Currently, the ERC project Di-Dip (PI Georg Vogeler, technical integration: Florian Atzenhofer Baumgartner, Computer Vision lead: Angelos Nicolaou) is developing a prototype of a new system called “MOM-NG” that leverages recent developments in machine learning. MOM-NG includes a flat file system based data model (fsdb) in which charters and collections as the main entities are organised in a hierarchy of folders. Based on fsdb, data processing pipelines, display and retrieval systems provide functionality in a microservice design pattern.

One component is an object detector based on YOLOv5 (Nicolaou 2022, Nicolaou et al. 2023). Object detection and classification are performed offline at approximately 10 images per second creating lightweight indexes with all detected objects. The objects can be searched and retrieved using a fast retrieval scheme. Classes can be searched quickly—retrieving results in milliseconds per thousand images. IIIF Image API enables extraction of image areas on demand. A prototype of this system showing the search for “wr:Ornament” (= decorative element in the writable area “img:WritableArea”) class can be seen in fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Screenshot from the image part extraction and retrieval app with the class “wr:Ornament”

This has a significant impact on IIIUrK: MOM-NG can delegate the preselection of relevant objects in a corpus to a machine. The IIIUrK project provides a detailed taxonomy

that is not covered by the current system as class occurrences are extremely rare compared to the full data set: for instance, IIIUrk Niveau 1 which comprises 8 sub classes has currently 5951 occurrences in more than 75,000 charters. For instance, in a set of 1,000 randomly selected charters, that we used for region annotation, none was labeled with this class. Nonetheless, already the generic “wr:Ornament” class provides a useful preselection. An optimised workflow using this can enable art historians to integrate more material in the IIIUrk-collection. MOM-NG's classification of image regions enables studying temporal and geographic patterns and allows statistical correlation with human-defined classes.

Finally, the MOM-NG system includes similarity search functionality based on pre-computed embeddings (see Wu et al. 2023). Fine-tuning large models pretrained on medieval charters, guided by expert input, and dimensionality reduction techniques like uniform manifold approximation and projection (UMAP) and vector quantization through compression codebooks accelerate search across feature spaces. The search infrastructure employs vector similarity search supporting both exact and approximate matching using learned indices and Graph Neural Networks to move beyond Hierarchical Navigable Small Worlds indexing (HNSW) as a baseline. We exploit and extend out-of-the-box solutions like Typesense for basic functionality, while key-value stores like Valkey enable custom re-ranking strategies and subspace search across specific attributes. This architecture allows discovery of charters through textual, visual, and structural modalities, including possible fusion of these. The existing corpus of illuminated charters and their detailed descriptions can thus guide searches for stylistically similar documents across the collection.

We consider the functionalities of MOM-NG as important tools to enhance search and analysis of illuminated charters if we can combine them with the existing data: preselection before manual description, expanding search by similarity to the already annotated documents, and analysing the distribution of features identified through the system. The poster will present MOM-NG's development as of early 2026 and use cases of the system from the IIIUrk project.

Credits & Acknowledgements

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